

High risk industries for advanced lightning protection system

Kalagotla Chenchireddy¹, P. Nagabushanam², Radhika Dora¹, Vadthya Jagan³,
Shabbier Ahmed Sydu⁴, Nunavath Praveen⁵

¹Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Geethanjali College of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India

²Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Vallurupalli Nageswara Rao Vignana Jyothi Institute of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India

³Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Vignana Bharathi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, India

⁴Department of Engineering, University of Technology and Applied Sciences Al-Musannah, Muladdah, Oman

⁵Projects, Cape Electric Pvt Ltd, Telangana, India

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ABSTRACT

Lightning strikes are a serious risk for high-risk facilities like oil and gas plants, mines, explosive storage, and data centers. These places hold the sensitive equipment and dangerous materials, and a lightning strike can cause major damage, leading to expensive downtime or even disastrous events such as fires or explosions. That's why having a strong lightning protection system is not just a matter of following rules, but it is crucial for protecting both people and property. The complete lightning protection solutions designed to meet the specific needs of these critical industries. The services include lightning simulations and both isolated and attached lightning protection systems. This study investigates the real-time installation and testing of advanced lightning protection systems across high-risk industries like oil and gas plants, mines, explosive storage, and data centers. This ensures that the facility stays safe and continues to operate, even during severe weather. By investing in an effective lightning protection system, you can help secure your assets and keep everyone safe, focusing on what really matters in your industry.

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Corresponding Author:

Kalagotla Chenchireddy

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Geethanjali College of Engineering and Technology
Hyderabad, India

Email: chenchireddy.kalagotla@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

There are so many issues happening in high-risk industries, like oil and gas plants, mines, explosive storage, and data centers. These places hold sensitive equipment and dangerous materials. During the lightning strike hit. It may be hit directly at the structure, fire exposures, or sensitive equipment. In this paper [1]-[3], the authors executed their solutions for this concern by determining the possibilities of lightning strikes hitting the industry buildings. And they planned to protect the internal equipment and workers during the lightning strikes. During the lightning strike, a large amount of energy will be generated that should cause damage to the structure, electrical and electronic equipment, workers, employees, and humans with lightning interactions and lifelines. To overcome the problem, the author implemented the solution, for this is they used wood, rocks, and clay to reduce conductivity. And this is another method for lightning protection for high-risk industries. Authors presented [4]-[7] the related interactions and safety measures during lightning strikes in high-risk industries. Many people don't know when lightning strikes happen in certain areas, such as construction areas, oil, and gas industries, and how to prevent them. Because 70-80% of the bolts of thunder spark reach the ground and ground objects are harmless, but the most

dangerous areas are construction areas and high-risk industries are most dangerous. Because the internal sensitive equipment will react very quickly. So, it will harm full and takes to death to the peoples like internal workers and employees, so in this paper, the authors use a lightning metal rod that is directly connected to the ground to discharge the lightning current.

Authors implemented in [8]-[13] metallic conductors to transfer electrical current into the ground for lightning current overvoltage protection. Because when lightning strikes happen on large buildings or industries, they may cause severe damage; that is why the authors came up with this solution. A lot of research is ongoing on these issues, but some problems still lack effective solutions. Therefore, we are implementing an advanced lightning protection system for high-risk industries. In this method, a large amount of lightning current is safely grounded. When a lightning strike hits high-risk industries, hospitals, and commercial buildings, a large amount of energy is generated, which may cause serious damage and losses. The damages and losses include structural damage, injury to living beings due to electric shock, physical damage, fire explosions, mechanical destruction, chemical release due to lightning current effects, internal system failures, loss of human life, disruption of public services, and cultural loss [14]-[20]. To minimize these damages and losses, we proposed a new solution, namely an advanced lightning protection system for high-risk industries. This system minimizes damages and losses during lightning strikes by following IS/IEC standards and by installing real-time down conductors and conducting real-time testing.

2. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram of high-risk industries for an advanced lightning protection system is shown in Figure 1. The overall process of the system works when a lightning strike happens in the high-risk industries and commercial buildings. and how the implemented system will work during lightning strikes. That will be explained in this paper. When a lightning strike or lightning flash happens in high-risk industries and commercial buildings, that time the large amount of energy is generated. That should damage the structure of the building and the damages and losses are structure damage, injury of living beings by electric shock, physical damage, fire explosion, mechanical destruction, chemical release due to lightning current effect, internal systems failures, loss of human life and service to the public and loss of culture. To minimize these, we came up with this new method called high-risk industries for an advanced lightning protection system, real-time installation, and testing. Our system works on one strategy, and we provide as two categories. One is a general lightning protection system, and another one is a special lightning protection system [21]-[25]. The general lightning protection system we follow is the one ICE 62305-3 standard, it is focus on the structure, physical damage, and life hazards. When a lightning flash happens in any high-risk industries or commercial buildings, this standard will be applied, and another one is the special protection system IEC 62305-4 it is focus on the designing, installation, inspection, maintenance, and testing of surge protection measures for electrical and electronics systems to reduce the risk of permanent failures due to lightning electromagnetic impulse within the structure. This standard focuses on the installation, inspection, maintenance, and testing to reduce the permanent failures from the surges during lightning strikes.

Figure 1. Block diagram of high-risk industries for advanced lightning protection system

3. METHOD

In this paper, we will explain the real industry selection, site selection, selection of materials, real-time installation, and real-time testing results in detail, and how industries deal with real-time lightning strikes in high-risk industries and buildings. The selection process is very important when installing a lightning protection system in high-risk industries and commercial buildings. We follow the IEC 62305 standard for selecting high-risk industries and commercial buildings. First, we will discuss high-risk industries [26]-[30]. In the selection of industries for a lightning protection system, we prefer high-risk industries because they contain sensitive equipment and dangerous materials, and a lightning strike can cause major damage to these industries. That is why we strongly recommend a lightning protection system for high-risk industries to protect equipment and human lives from lightning strikes. The selection of high-risk buildings is also important because it depends on the height of the buildings. We prefer buildings above 15 meters in height for installing the lightning protection system because buildings above 15 meters have a higher chance of being struck by lightning. Therefore, we prefer to install lightning protection systems in buildings above 15 meters in height, whether in hospitals or commercial buildings.

Materials used description of lightning protection system used: In the high-risk industries for advanced lightning protection systems, we used some materials. There are 10 mm MS (mild steel) solid round down conductor, 10 mm copper bonded solid round conductor, earth stud, conductor holder, 10 mm MS and stainless steel (SS) cross link connector, vertical air terminal, lightning event counter, MMR-620, and Vernier scale. The functions of these materials are explained as follows. The 10 mm MS solid round down conductor is used for discharging or grounding the lightning strike current. This conductor grounds the large amount of high current without disturbing the internal lines in the high-risk industries and commercial buildings.

Another one is 10 mm copper bonded solid round conductor: This 10 mm copper bonded solid round conductor is also used for grounding purpose and it has higher conductivity compared to MS conductor, but it is more expensive compared to MS conductor. Another one is earth stud: This earth stud is used for earthing and testing purpose because the continuity test is performed by connecting the earth stud. Mainly, it is used for earthing in the high-risk industries. Conductor holder: conductor holder is used for holding purpose on the parapet wall to avoid disturbances from the wind and rainfall. 10 mm MS and SS cross link connector: 10 mm MS and SS cross link connector is used for connecting the two conductors in cross direction for looping purposes. Vertical air terminal: This vertical air terminal is used for catching or collecting lightning strikes. It is connected with down conductor to pass the lightning strike current to the ground. Lightning event counter: Lightning event counter is used to count the lightning strikes. It stores the data with date, time, and year in the memory card. MMR-620: MMR-620 is a testing device used for continuity testing in the high-risk industries and commercial buildings to check whether the lightning protection system is systematically installed or not. Vernier scale: Vernier scale is used for conductor thickness checking purpose.

4. REAL-TIME INSTALLATION PROCESS

This section discusses the real-time installation process in detail for the lightning protection system for high-risk industries. The installation process is very important for any real-time system before testing the system in real time. In these high-risk industries, the advanced lightning protection system is installed step by step by following the guidelines. Figure 2 shows the connection of the earth stud with the MS solid round conductor inside the wall. In our installation process, we use the MS solid round conductor from below ground level to the top floor of the industries or commercial buildings. The MS conductor is connected with the earth stud on each floor, and it is also connected with many other devices and materials such as the vertical air terminal and lightning event counter [31]-[35]. These are the main components of the advanced lightning protection system for high-risk industries. Without these components, we cannot test the lightning protection system properly or obtain accurate results. Figure 3 shows the installation of the MS solid round conductor with the conductor holder. The MS solid round conductor is used to carry the lightning current to the ground. This conductor runs along all sides of the buildings. Figure 4 discusses the installation of the vertical air terminal. In real time, the air terminal catches the lightning strikes and passes the lightning current through the MS solid round conductor to the ground level without disturbing the internal equipment of the industries or commercial buildings. Figure 5 shows the installation of the lightning event counter. The lightning event counter is connected to the MS solid round conductor to record lightning strike events. Table 1 shows the predefined values of the MMR-620 device.

Figure 2. Connection of the earth stud with an MS solid round conductor inside the wall

Figure 3. Real-time installation of an MS solid round conductor

Figure 4. Installation of a vertical air terminal

Figure 5. Installation of the lightning event counter

Table1. MMR-620 device predefined values

Range	Resolution	Test current	Accuracy
0...999 $\mu\Omega^*$	1 $\mu\Omega$	10 A	± (0.25% m.v. + 2 digits)
1.000...1.999 m Ω	0.001 m Ω	10 A	
2.00...19.99 m Ω	0.01 m Ω	10 A	
20.0...199.9 m Ω	0.1 m Ω	1 A	
200...999 m Ω	1 m Ω	0.1 A	
1.000...1.999 Ω	0.001 Ω	0.1 A	
2.00...19.99 Ω	0.01 Ω	10 mA	
20.0...199.9 Ω	0.1 Ω	1 mA	
200...1999 Ω	1 Ω	0.1 mA	

5. REAL-TIME INSTALLATION TESTING RESULTS

In real-time testing of high-risk industries for an advanced lightning protection system, the connections, equipotential bindings, earthing conductors, and continuity test are checked first in the industries and commercial buildings. This continuity test is very important because it defines whether the lightning protection system is properly installed or not. We use some devices to check the continuity test, but the most commonly used device is the MMR-620. This device gives accurate results for the continuity test. Figure 6 shows the MMR-620 device, and Figure 7 explains the working of the MMR-620 device. This device helps to check the connections, equipotential bindings, earthing conductors, and continuity test in the lightning protection system. While testing the lightning protection system for high-risk industries, we check the connections, equipotential bindings, earthing conductors, and continuity test using this device. The predefined testing value is 0.2 ohms. If the device exceeds this value during testing, it means that the installation is not properly completed or the conductor is not properly installed. These are the main reasons for this problem during the testing process [36]-[40]. Table 2 shows the output results for the lightning protection system.

Table 2. Output results for the lightning protection system

Tested output results	MMR-620		
	Range value	Test current	Accuracy
33.0 m Ω	20.0...199.9 m Ω	1 A	± (0.25% m.v. + 2 digits)
14.2 m Ω	2.00...19.99 m Ω	10 A	
86.48 m Ω	20.0...199.9 Ω	1 mA	

Figure 6. MMR-620 continuity test device in off position

Figure 7. MMR-620 continuity test value

Figure 8 shows the testing in commercial buildings. Figure 9 describes the lightning protection system testing on connections, equipotential bindings, earthing conductors, and continuity test for another MS solid round conductor in the commercial building. Figure 10 shows the lightning event counter. The lightning event counter is used for storing the data of lightning strikes with time and date. When lightning strikes happen in high-risk industries, the lightning event counter stores the lightning strike data in digital form.

Figure 8. Testing in a commercial building

Figure 9. MMR-620 continuity test for random MS solid round conductor

Figure 10. Lightning event counter

6. CONCLUSION

This paper gives a solution for lightning strikes. Lightning strikes are very dangerous to high-risk industry facilities such as oil and gas plants, mines, explosive storage facilities, and data centers. These places often contain sensitive equipment and dangerous materials, and a lightning strike can cause major damage, leading to expensive downtime or even disastrous events such as fires or explosions. Having a strong isolated lightning protection system for high-risk industries is not just a matter of following rules, but it is also crucial for protecting both people and property. The complete lightning protection solutions are designed to meet the specific needs of these critical industries. The services include lightning simulations and both isolated and attached lightning protection systems. Our aim is to provide electrically insulated solutions with down conductors and lightning rods that can handle up to 100,000 volts. This ensures that the facilities stay safe and continue to operate even during severe weather conditions. By investing in effective lightning protection systems, industries can secure their assets and improve overall safety.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Kalagotla	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
Chenchireddy														
P. Nagabushanam		✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Radhika Dora	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓
Vadthya Jagan				✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓		✓
Shabbier Ahmed Sydu	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓
Nunavath Praveen	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability is not applicable to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Dr. Kalagotla Chenchireddy was born in Andhra Pradesh State, India, in 1990. He received his Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) and Master of Technology (M.Tech.) from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University (JNTU), Hyderabad, India, in 2011 and 2013, respectively, and completed his Ph.D. degree in the Department of Electrical Engineering from Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Karunyanagar, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, in 2024. He is presently working as an associate professor at Geethanjali College of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India. He has presented technical papers at various national and international conferences. He has published research papers in various Scopus-indexed and Web of Science-indexed journals. His areas of interest include power electronics, power quality, and multilevel inverters. He is a regular reviewer for *ISA Transactions*, *Cybernetics and Systems Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE)* journals, *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, and *International Journal of Applied Power Engineering (IJAPE)*. He can be contacted at email: chenchireddy.kalagotla@gmail.com.

Dr. P. Nagabushanam completed his Doctor of Philosophy in 2020 with research focused on EEG for medical applications using machine learning and deep learning algorithms for EEG signals. He had been the Co-Principal Investigator (Co-PI) for a Department of Science and Technology (DST) funded project worth 48 lakhs (DST/TSG/ICT/2015/54G, 2nd May 2016), and qualified for the Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering (GATE) examination in 2019, 2018, 2013, and 2010. He has 39 Scopus-indexed publications, including 7 Science Citation Index (SCI) indexed publications, 8 Scopus journal publications, 24 Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Scopus-indexed conference publications, and 2 book chapters. He also completed 6 Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) through the National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL) and 3 All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) Academy for Learning and Teaching (ATAL) courses. He had been involved as a coordinator in organizing training programs/workshops, and he had been an exam coordinator, Eduserve software coordinator, and GATE coaching coordinator in the department for more than 8 years. His research areas include EEG for medical applications and Electrical Power Systems. He has 13 years of teaching experience and 2 years of industry experience. He is presently working as an assistant professor in the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering at Vallurupalli Nageswara Rao Vignana Jyothi Institute of Engineering and Technology (VNR VJIET), Hyderabad. He can be contacted at email: nagabushanamphd14@gmail.com.

Dr. Radhika Dora is currently serving as a professor and head of the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering. She earned her Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) degree in electrical and electronics engineering from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University Anantapur (JNTUA) in 2000, followed by an M.Tech. degree in Electrical Power Engineering from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University Hyderabad (JNTUH) in 2007. She received her Ph.D. degree in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from JNTUH in 2017. Her research interests focus on power quality problems and mitigation, renewable energy generation, and electric vehicle design. She can be contacted at email: drradhikadora.eee@gcet.edu.in.

Dr. Vadthya Jagan was born in Telangana State, India, in 1985. He received his B.Tech. degree in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from C.V.R College of Engineering, Hyderabad, Telangana State, in 2007, and his M.Tech. degree in Electric Drives and Power Electronics from the Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, Uttarakhand, India, in 2011. From August 2011 to July 2013, he worked as an assistant professor at Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India. He completed his Ph.D. degree in the Department of Electrical Engineering from the Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, Uttarakhand, India, in 2018. He worked as an associate professor at Vignana Bharathi Institute of Technology (VBIT), Hyderabad, Telangana State, India, from July 2018 to August 2023. Presently, he has been working as a professor in the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering at VBIT since September 2023. Currently, he is working on the Research Promotion Scheme (RPS) project titled "Analysis, Design, and Implementation of Extreme-Boost Quasi Z-Source Inverter Topologies," sanctioned by the All-India Council for Technical Education (AICTE). His current research interests include power electronics, development of novel topologies for Z-source inverters and DC-DC converters, and solar photovoltaic systems. He can be contacted at email: jagan.iitr@gmail.com.

Dr. Shabbier Ahmed Sydu is a distinguished researcher and scholar with a strong academic background in the field of Electrical and Electronics Engineering. He obtained his Ph.D. from Sri Satya Sai University of Technology and Medical Sciences, India, where his research focused on advancing the integration of solar and wind energy into existing power systems. Before his doctoral studies, he earned his M.Tech. degree from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University (JNTU) Kakinada, India, where he further developed his expertise in power electronics and drives. He completed his B.Tech. degree from Acharya Nagarjuna University, India, where he laid the foundation for his career in engineering. He can be contacted at email: shabbier.sydu@utas.edu.om.

Nunavath Praveen received his B.Tech. from JNTU Hyderabad, India, in 2024 in the Department of Electrical Engineering. He is presently working as a Graduate Engineer Trainee at Projects Cape Electric Pvt Ltd, Telangana, India. He has presented technical papers in various national and international conferences. He can be contacted at email: praveennunavath3@gmail.com.